

International relations and alternating diplomacy in foreign trade operations

Dr. Erik Obiol Anaya
Dr. Jesús Gonzales Herrera
Ms. Cesar Perez Baquedano

ABSTRACT: Balochistan, a geopolitically significant province in Pakistan, faces profound educational challenges exacerbated by its unique socio-political and ethnic landscape. Despite its strategic importance and vast natural resources, the region suffers from low human development indicators, influenced by ongoing insurgencies, international interference, and a significant refugee influx. The educational sector, particularly in early grades, reflects this stagnation, with curriculum and language policies that do not cater to the region's ethnolinguistic diversity. This paper investigates the impact of these policies on educational outcomes in Balochistan, where the imposition of Urdu and an irrelevant curriculum undermine effective learning. Drawing on Culturally Relevant Pedagogy (CRP), it argues for a curriculum that acknowledges and incorporates the cultural and linguistic realities of Balochistan. The research underscores the importance of mother/home language instruction in early grades, advocating for a curriculum that reflects the daily lives and experiences of the students. The analysis highlights how current practices contribute to ethnic disharmony and poor learning outcomes, proposing a shift towards a more inclusive and contextually appropriate educational framework to foster better educational achievements and social cohesion in the province.

Keywords: Culturally Relevant Pedagogy, Mother/Home Language Instruction, Curriculum Contextualization, Educational Outcomes in Balochistan

Introduction

Background and Context

Literature Review

Successful Initiatives and Case Studies

Recommendations

Challenges and Opportunities

Conclusions

References

1. Introduction

The rigidity and formalization of the classic concept of diplomacy apparently excludes any positive relationship between civil society and the international environment. For classical theory, the term diplomacy is defined in the following four points: "it is a specific activity of the States; it lies in the sphere of competence of the government and is carried out by ministerial officials specially prepared for it; it is developed within the framework of "an international society characterized by the autonomy of the States; and its purpose is none other than to execute the fundamental guidelines of the state's foreign policy, However, in a modern environment we can observe that authors such as Zidane Zeraoui (2016), citing Cornago, indicate that paradiplomacy is the participation of non-

central governments in international relations through the establishment of ad hoc contacts with private entities, or public bodies from abroad, in order to promote socioeconomic and cultural issues, as well as any other external dimension of its constitutional powers.

2. Background and Context

International relations are links between actors that allow us to live in a globalized world without borders, with the capacity to interconnect the knowledge of peoples, through intercultural communication that facilitates the flow of ideas and the exchange of experiences in different aspects of social life, achieving substantial improvements for production.

To better understand the idea of this research, Calduch (1991) defines international relations as the discipline that results from the interaction between certain international actors, taking into account a defined space and time, in such a way that they constitute an intelligible process as a whole and outside of which each of these interactions lacks meaning. Likewise, Lozano (2001), quoting Schwarzenberger, states that international relations are a branch of sociology that has international society as its object of study, adding that international affairs are the relations between groups and individuals, which affect society as such.

Once the concept of international relations has been understood, it is important to emphasize the term actors, since this term is quite common, within the legal custom that moves within the international sphere. When talking about actors, reference is made to the groups or individuals that interact in this system and because of the relationships that occur between them, the media and the messages that produce a positive and/or negative effect on the decision-making of the individuals who inhabit society. Likewise, according to Lozano (2001), he indicates that there are two types of actors: the first, called state actors, which refer to States and governmental or intergovernmental organizations; and the second, called non-state actors, which include members of such as civil society, NGOs that have also been gaining a great deal of participation in the sector over time and transnational forces, which have been gaining participation substantially over the course of recent decades.

Finally, regardless of the type of actor, what they seek is to maintain bonds of friendship, cooperation and respect with all members of the international community. In addition to promoting a foreign policy and building lasting fraternal relations between the various nations or between them and international society. All this will only be possible by having a good management of international relations.

2.1. International Relations in the 21st Century

Today, international relations are marked by the era of globalization, which has been influenced by the growing rise of information and communication technologies. In the twenty-first century, the role played by intra-national actors such as regions, municipalities or their associations, as well as private entities made up of members of civil society, in

international relations is increasingly marked and has also generated blocs, which, for ideological reasons, have achieved an exponential level of growth through social networks.

Librado Orozco (2016) states that the more active participation of new actors in international relations is a positive feature in the globalization process, because it contributes to integration, understanding, and shared progress in the international context. Globalization generates a new structure and dynamics in the international system because it is expressed in the interconnection and dynamism between nations and individuals who seek to excel at the international level.

On the social and cultural level, the interconnectedness of the world is more evident. Due to the interaction made by individuals from two or more different cultures, interculturality is generated, this originates integration, respect for other cultures, dialogue and cooperation. This phase of globalization also goes hand in hand with the knowledge of different languages by individuals, because this achieves a greater understanding between cultures.

On the other hand, there are other factors that have generated changes in international relations such as climate change, the political and economic problems of countries, migration and diseases; all this has caused the globalization process to alter the nature of power and the relations between actors in the political system in order to generate different opportunities to strengthen its take-off and development. In addition, it should be noted that, although the globalization process generates challenges for developing nations, it also poses opportunities, especially for subnational actors who must make their best effort to achieve external action that reflects the interests of each nation (Orozco, 2016).

In today's world, thanks to the global situation and the embrace of new technologies, the different institutions have realized that they themselves can connect to the world, to make their interests known and to establish links with other actors; without the need for traditional diplomacy, which is executed when international relations are channeled into a country's Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

The actors of the international system have realized that they can do the same as diplomats to obtain benefits for their institution, economic income, projects and alliances for their common good and their internationalization. That is why they seek to establish direct channels of dialogue among themselves to build cooperative links that allow them to develop in different areas of human life. In this complex field that demands knowledge, cooperation tools and their own skills, institutions must internationalize if they do not disappear.

Thus, in this first section, the influence of globalization in the field of international relations in the twenty-first century has been detailed. In this way, we understand that globalization

It is not simply a new way of seeing and feeling the world, it also means a new way of being in it, a new lifestyle that requires a different and specialized learning, to

successfully face the challenges presented by the new international order that demands, more and more, to think globally and act locally (Sam Black, 2000).

3. Literature Review

3.1 The new disciplines of international relations

Now that we have a clearer vision of the concept of international relations and the role that globalization plays in this context, it is necessary to complement what has been researched with the new disciplines that are developing on the margins of the evolution of international relations.

Esther Barbé (1995) defines international relations as a discipline that contributes to the understanding, evaluation and control of relations between States and the universal community in terms of history, science, philosophy and art. This definition allows us to understand the evolution of the disciplines that concern international relations, which years ago were political science, history, international law, sociology and economics.

Currently, due to the changes that have taken place in this century, new disciplines of international relations have been formed: citizen diplomacy, public diplomacy, cultural management and paradiplomacy.

3.1.1. Citizen diplomacy. It is the means of informative, peaceful and institutionalized communication between the actors of the international system, which aims to create a communication link between the actors, so that they can know each other's interests and try to resolve their differences in a negotiated manner, through cooperation and understanding (Antón, 1996). In a democratic society, citizen diplomacy plays an important role, since it is an alternative for the resolution of conflicts between nations and within the country, without it, society would not function correctly because it is the citizens who organize themselves to achieve their specific objectives and projects that ensure the common good, achieving that society is consolidated in a mature democracy.

3.1.2. Public diplomacy. It is defined as public and private attempts that aim to influence the political opinion of foreign countries to establish channels of communication with a specific public or with a general public for the benefit of the common good (Antón, 1996). The actors that make up public diplomacy are international organizations and governments that seek to influence foreign audiences to improve the image of the country, to influence the public they are targeting and, above all, to improve the situation abroad.

Finally, it should be noted that the term public diplomacy, despite being recent in the language of international relations, reflects what has always been present in the interaction of different international actors: the ability to communicate, to weave alliances and to achieve greater influence on the global scene. (Ágreda, Rubio, & Manfredi, 2014)

3.1.3. Cultural Management. It is the professional work that is responsible for putting culture in contact with society. It does so through programs, projects, cultural activities that are born at the initiative of the actors of a society.

The work is carried out by a cultural manager who is working for an institution or a community and seeks to contribute to the culture of that specific place, in this case, when talking about culture, emphasis is placed on the values, attitudes and vision of the world on the part of individuals (Cañola, 2013). Peru has an intense intercultural system that through international relations would generate a great impact on society, which is why culture is a key piece for the development of a society.

3.1.4. Paradiplomacy. It is a complementary and sometimes essential activity of diplomacy. This form of diplomacy is born from contact with people and is the predecessor of formal relations and differs from formal diplomacy because the latter takes place between governments or states and represents the whole of society. In addition, due to the globalized world, the decentralization of the State and world changes, more possibilities are opening for the regions, thus achieving what paradiplomacy is (Zanin, 2007). Finally, paradiplomacy in international relations appears as a response to the inability of the State to solve the problems presented by civil society.

4. Successful Initiatives and Case Studies

International relations have undergone substantial changes that have made it possible to shape the interaction between nations and the development of non-governmental actors, achieving the creation of new forms of communication without the need for State intervention. This new form of communication is called paradiplomacy.

As is already known, the technological, economic and cultural changes that have taken place in recent years have created changes in the most important actor in a society, the State. The state actor does not have the capacity to control issues such as: the quality of life of citizens, social exclusion, urban services; which has generated that different actors such as NGOs, universities, institutions focus on creating different ways of doing international relations on their own. (Miranda, 2005)

Likewise, to understand paradiplomacy it is important to know that it comes from the prefix "para" which means "parallel to", "next to" or "associated". Considering this prefix, paradiplomacy is defined as a diplomacy parallel to traditional diplomacy that works with the aim of benefiting a specific non-governmental actor.

However, it is important to broaden the term paradiplomacy and not only relate it to sub-state government entities, but also to other state actors in the international system. James Der Derian, quoted by Flores (2007), states that paradiplomacy includes "any form of international activity carried out by non-state actors".

Paradiplomacy is a term that has been used frequently in recent years, even though there is still no concrete definition of what it means. That is why there are many authors who define it and work based on these concepts, such as Pedro Lozano Bartolozzi and Zidane Zeraoui.

Lozano (2001) defines paradiplomacy as a means of informative, peaceful and institutionalized communication among the actors of the international system; with the

purpose of establishing communication between the actors to know the different interests between them and thus resolve differences in a negotiable way, promoting international relations based on cooperation and understanding.

On the other hand, Zeraoui states that paradiplomacy is an activity that includes all actors that have an international activity, whether state or non-state. In addition, he affirms that paradiplomacy has a poorly mediatized, confusing, complex character and has a low profile in the mass media; but that, despite this, in recent times has become a main topic in universities. (Zeraoui, 2016)

It should be noted that paradiplomacy is also known as decentralized diplomacy, which has emerged due to new forms and methods of international relations that go beyond traditional diplomatic practices. This new form of communication must concentrate on local needs, because the management of the specific issues of external action cannot be focused on detail by the State itself. (Orozco, 2016)

Finally, because of all the changes generated by the globalization process, non-state actors have found in this new discipline of paradiplomacy an effective means to promote their internationalization, raise capital, develop projects, development tools and establish alliances according to their interests.

4.1 The importance of paradiplomacy

Paradiplomacy plays an important role in this century because it is an era of many changes, this new discipline is a form of communication that seeks to make non-state institutions seek their own benefits. It should be noted that paradiplomacy is not intended to replace official diplomacy, but rather acts in parallel to it to complement it. Both are important in the process of international relations.

The main objective of paradiplomacy is the development of actors and their connection with the world. This discipline is important because it creates ties and relations with the outside world and is closely related to integration, understood as cooperation, between various actors, with the aim of creating greater economic, political and cultural development; paradiplomacy is exercised correctly when it is responsible for guiding the foreign policy of the central states.

In this sense, Rudón (2010) clarifies that integration allows us to know and get closer to other cultures, consolidate common projects and objectives between citizens and different countries, for their well-being and development. This central purpose of paradiplomacy, integration, covers different issues such as the national, political, social, environmental and educational agenda.

In this research, we will work with a non-state actor: the university. In this case, to understand what paradiplomacy is, we realize that the university has the capacity to make international relations, to design a foreign policy, to make its interests known to the world and to seek benefits that allow its growth. The university, thanks to paradiplomacy, can connect its institution to the world.

Likewise, the process of globalization of a university is of great importance because it is a stage of general evolution of the entity, which is why it generates changes in its times, characteristics and results; as well as with its organizational structures and the strategies of the house of studies. (Ríos, 2007)

Once the basic concepts to understand international relations and paradiplomacy have been consolidated, the following sections will seek to expand the information on the development over time of this science and the importance of having an international relations office in a university, this office must be active and capable to achieve the internationalization of the institution.

4.2 Channels of paradiplomacy

In this era of globalization, universities, through paradiplomacy, seek to connect and strengthen their relations with the foreigner; they do so through direct channels of dialogue to build cooperative links that allow them to reach a level of development in different aspects of human life.

According to Herrera (2008), non-state actors are considered international when they follow the attributes of having a degree of autonomy, are able to mobilize resources for internationalization, are influential and achieve their objectives and, finally, have continuity in their developed functions.

Likewise, universities are global institutions that need to maintain a relationship with different entities in a professional way, which demands knowledge, tools and skills from the field of International Relations; because if institutions are not internationalized, they will disappear.

As stated by Michilot (2008), the university, due to the phenomenon of globalization, the mobility of students and teachers has increased, through the modality of exchanges and internships in order to publicize the potential of this house of studies worldwide.

University paradiplomacy is reflected through the creation and good performance of international relations offices, which serve as tools to promote exchanges with neighboring countries and work on educational policies. According to that, these offices are responsible for providing enriching experiences to students, teachers and researchers who leave the country on behalf of the university.

4.2.1. International Relations Offices

According to Ramírez (1996), the communication offices are active, organized and stable sources that provide information to cover communication needs and transmit a positive image of the institution and influence public opinion. In addition, he affirms that they are organized because they must be in a specific place that is easily accessible and are stable because they operate throughout the year continuously, all to achieve their stated purposes and obtain good internal and external communication.

Portugal (2008) defines the International Relations Offices (IROs) as an organized unit that is responsible for the international policy of an institution, which channels the interaction, cooperation and relations established with other institutions and organizations worldwide.

The objective of the cabinets is the projection, strengthening and competitiveness in the work of the institution, in this case the university, in the global world. These offices need staff capable of designing foreign policy, organizing and managing international activities, channeling international relations and projecting a good image of the university. This unit is the main contact between the institution and the outside.

On the other hand, for the operation of cabinets or offices, some criteria must be followed: first, it is important to evaluate the profile of the office workers, who must be characterized by having ease of communication and listening in an efficient and cordial way; secondly, the university must be clear about the goals that the institution seeks in the international framework in order to be able to propose concrete actions that allow it to achieve goals in a certain period; thirdly, to know the international context in which the university operates, which are the actors involved, how these actors act and thus be able to effectively reach the public you want to reach and establish new contacts worldwide; finally, it is also essential to maintain the culture of the institution to establish coherence between the internal and external communication of the university.

5. Recommendations

There is an integration and importance of the roles played by the international relations offices in a university, in order to get the most out of integration and cooperation, thus achieving an international impact of the university. This theoretical approach is further complemented by the study carried out by Portugal (2008) who assures that the objectives of this unit are achieved due to a series of activities typical of the IROs that favor the internationalization of the institution, through information, advice and promotion activities, the most common being:

- Development of programs and calls within the Strategic Plan on internationalization issues.
- Promote the signing of international agreements.
- Provide information on the different international cooperation programs in the corresponding field.
- Participation in social networks, which has great weight due to the process of globalization.
- Coordinate and promote national and international scientific events organized by the institution.
- Facilitate staff mobility at the international level.
- Support the training of your staff through courses taught in different languages.
- Advise exchangers.
- Plan activities according to the culture of the country in which you are going to participate.
- To report on the economic, social, political, cultural structure and other areas.
- Seek the support of personalities and opinion leaders.

- Language is an important factor, therefore, you must have translation experts capable of communicating through digital and print media.

6. Challenges and Opportunities

Since its inception, multiple difficulties have existed for this type of international relations, which, in general, have always led to the understanding that only States and some types of international organizations could carry out actions that fit within the analysis of what is understood as international relations. However, little by little in the 2000s it began to be seen that there was also participation by transnational corporations and even in government entities that had not been authorized or that had received direct power from the state to carry out this type of activities.

Perhaps the greatest difficulties in the application of alternative diplomacy lie in carrying out adequate action by the entities that carry out this type of activity, in order not to alter the state's foreign policy with it, which could generate friction. at the governmental level or at the political level, especially in countries such as Latin America where there are a large number of disparate political groups where each one has its own agenda that is not necessarily interconnected with the government plans, this could to a certain extent affect the sovereignty of the state. or the personification of the same by the rulers.

The second point to take into account regarding the application of paradiplomacy is the real capacity to prepare this type of international policies, and in addition to this the lack of an entity that can monitor that these actions or plans comply with what is indicated in the preceding paragraph, that is, they do not overlap with the interests of the state and generate an alteration to the plans of the central government.

On the other hand, among the main strengths of alternative diplomacy we can find that each local government knows its problems better and that leads them to make decisions that could be more precise than those taken by the central government.

Likewise, another of the strengths is that regardless of the political color of the central government, in relation to that of each local government, alternative diplomacy means that own public policies can be established in parallel, which means that even in cases of political discrepancies or ideological differences between local and national authorities, this does not generate difficulties for community members.

7. Conclusions

Although the phenomenon, now natural, of globalization has established changes in the mentality of people and societies, aimed at the formation of a common thought or ideology, we can see that in turn, currently cities and regions have taken a greater role than the central governments themselves, generating effects like commonwealths, and thus seeing the resurgence of even cultures or languages that have already disappeared, such as Muchick in the north of Peru, which has allowed us to

find a logical need for this figure of alternative diplomacy, in the search to protect identities specific to each region.

This identity of each local government in principle should not oppose the public policies of the central government, at least not in a frontal and direct manner, but it is possible that depending on the ruler who is in executive functions of the state, there may be to a certain extent, a conflict, at least in matters of political interests, between national and local authority.

Although this discrepancy, at least possible, in public policies can generate a certain level of political confrontation, we should not really see paradiplomacy as a risk to the integrity of the state or its public policies, but rather as an additional tool that could even offload the overload on the central government for more efficient management of the regions.

Due to everything mentioned in this research, it can finally be concluded that alternative diplomacy or paradiplomacy turns out to be an extremely efficient public management tool for local governments, which can generate windows that can provide benefits in different areas for the defense of their local identities and thus establish close ties in a more agile way and avoiding to a certain extent the bureaucratic tangles that exist in Latin American governments.

8. References

1. Ágreda, E. P., Rubio, R., & Manfredi, J. L. (2014). *La diplomacia pública como reto de la política exterior*. Madrid : Oficina de información diplomática .
2. Antón, F. G. (1996). *Cómo reconocer si es una democracia lo que se tiene delante*. Madrid: Ediciones Internacionales Universitarias.
3. Barbé, E. (1995). *Relaciones Internacionales*. Madrid: Tecnos.
4. Calduch, R. (1991). *Relaciones Internacionales*. Madrid: Ciencias Sociales.
5. Cañola, K. (30 de septiembre de 2013). Universidad de Piura. Obtenido de <http://udep.edu.pe/hoy/2013/la-gestion-cultural-es-clave-para-el-desarrollo-de-una-sociedad-cultural/>
6. Flores, R. V. (2007). *La paradiplomacia mexicana: las relaciones exteriores de las entidades federativas*. México : CIDE .
7. Herrera, H. (31 de julio de 2008). *Blog de análisis político e internacional* . Obtenido de <https://nohoch-balam.blogspot.com/2008/07/la-paradiplomacia-en-la-actualidad.html>
8. Lozano, P. (2001). *De los imperios a la globalización: las relaciones internacionales en el siglo XX*. Pamplona, España: EUNSA.
9. Michilot, S. d. (2008). *Implementación de la Oficina de Relaciones Internacionales en la Universidad Nacional de Piura*. Piura : s/e.
10. Miranda, R. (2005). *Paradiplomacia y gobierno local: indicios de un modo diferente de hacer relaciones internacionales* . Buenos Aires: Instituto de Relaciones Internacionales .
11. Orozco, L. (2016). *Los actores subnacionales en la nueva fase del proceso de globalización* . *Revista de Comunicación*, 184-185 .
12. Portugal, L. (2008). *Los Gabinetes de Relaciones Internacionales* . Perú: s/e.
13. Ramírez, T. (1996). *Gabinetes de Comunicación: funciones, disfunciones e incidencia*. España: Bosch.
14. Ríos, A. S. (2007). *Internacionalización de las empresas latinoamericanas* . Perú: Fondo Editorial de la Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú.
15. Rudón, K. A. (2010). *La integración andina a partir de la sociedad civil: visiones en pugna en un escenario globalizado*. *Académica de la Federación Latinoamericana de Facultades de Comunicación Social* , 2-9 .
16. Zanin, E. (24 de agosto de 2007). *RegionNorteGrande Argentina* . Obtenido de <https://www.regionnortegrande.com.ar/?articulo=977>

-
17. Zeraoui, Z. (2016). Para entender la paradiplomacia . Bogotá : Desafíos.